

A Magnificent Gaᅅgadhara Image in Bengal Art

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Abstract

This paper highlights on the Gaᅅgadhara image in Bengal art which is recovered from the archaeological site Deulbari area of South Twenty Four Parganas, West Bengal. Gaᅅgadhara one of important forms of *Śiva* has been recovered from different parts of India. The sculptures of this particular image are not found in Bengal art. This paper aims to highlight the benedictory verses of literary and inscriptional reference which focuses the aesthetic importance of this image.

Key Words: Iconographic form, reference of literary and inscriptional source, image of Bengal

Introduction

The images of *Śiva* are normally categorised into two foremost forms, which signify more about his moods. One is the *soumya* or *māᅅgalika* form, where he is manifested in a more peaceful,

loving and romantic mood; the other is *ugra* form where he is personified as a killer, attacking a demon in his more aggressive and violent moods. The major forms of *Śiva* in *soumya rūpa*, which are delineated in the *āgamas* and various *śilpa-sastras* are of Gaṅgadhara, Chandraśekhara, Umā-Maheśvara, Kalyānsundara, Somaskandha and Ravanānugraha etc.

The popular story about *Śiva* holding *Gaṅgā* on his head is meet with in the Rāmāyana, Mahābhārata, Puraāṇa and āgamic literature. The popular story of *Gaṅgā*'s descent from heaven are narrated in the Mahābhārata (Vanaparva 108-109), the Rāmāyana (I.38-44), the Vishnu-purāna(IV.4), the Bhāgavata-Purāna(IX.9), Brahmaṇḍa-Purāna (2.3.56 23-57, 2.3.63.164-69), the Śiva-purāna(5.38-39), the Mārkaṇḍeya Purāna(56.1-18). The Kurma Purāna(I.35.35 &37.8-9) and Liṅga Purāna also describe this image of *Śiva*.

Literary Source

A comprehensive description of this delightful and interesting form of *Śiva* is to be found in the *Vanaparva* section of Mahābhārata. The story may briefly be stated below:

The descent of the heavenly Ganges to the earth was just to purify the ashes of the sinful sons of Sagara. Bhāgīratha, a later member the same family performed rigorous austerities to invoke the divine river *Gaṅgā*. The latter was pleased with Bhāgīratha but the force of her descent was such that the earth was unable to bear the shock. So Bhāgīratha prayed to *Śiva* to receive *Gaṅgā* on his head. *Śiva*, satisfied with the austerities of Bhāgīratha, accepted to receive the *Gaṅgā* in his matted locks. The river, proud of her mighty force, came down with all her vigour as if to crush *Śiva*, but found herself lost in the tangled mass of Siva's locks before she was able to reach the earth. At the request of Bhāgīratha *Śiva* let her flow down on earth from his locks in a tiny trickle. The river-goddess, the heavenly Ganges, is believed since then to abide in *Śiva*'s matted hair as one of his consorts (Buiteen, 1978, pp.424-30).

The pride of *Gaṅgā* and the anger of *Siva* are also emphasized in the *Matsya Purāna* where she was divided into seven streams(CXXI31-34):

She first on the head of the mighty lord *Śiva*, who curbed Her force by His glory. Her water's falling on the Earth, owing to *Śiva*'s anger, formed the Bindu lake. When she was thus suddenly stopped by *Śiva*, she became angry as she understood his unkind motive and an attempt to force Herself into the lower regions, having engulfed *Śiva* in her tumultuous current. *Śiva* realising this proud attitude of *Gaṅges*, thought about absorbing her within himself. At the moment he perceived *Bhāgīratha* standing in front of him and remembering his past austerities and hearing the entreaties of *Brahmā*, he suppressed his wrath and let the river loose in seven branches (Taluqdar,1916, pp.326-327).

According to *Śiva-Purāna*(5.38.41-57), the sacrificial horse was stolen by *Indra* and was regained from the ocean by *Sāgara* through boons granted to him by *Viṣṇu*. Four of the sixty thousand sons were spared, becoming kings that established his line. One of them name *Pañcajana*, begot *Aṁsumat*, whose grandson *Bhāgīratha* brought *Gaṅgā* to the sea and made her his daughter (5.39.6-8) (Shastri(ed)1970,pp.1610-12).

The vivid description of *Gaṅgāvatarana* has been depicted by *Nīlakantha Sastri* in his book *Gaṅgāvatarana*. According to him *Śiva*'s *Jaṭās* looked fresh but wash and, delighted with the serpents undisturbed, the moon unruffled and the crescent adornment of fresh flowers unaffected; only their perfume was increase by the sweet smelling blossoms of the celestial trees washed in abundance onto *Śiva*'s locks by the heavenly stream (*Sivarammurti* ,1976), pp,9-10) .

EPIGRAPHICAL RECORD

The epigraphical evidences vividly describe the *Gaṅgadhara* image of *Siva*. The *Allahabad Prasasti* of *Samudragupta* has mentioned that “*Gaṅgā* purifies all the three worlds as she flows quickly after being liberated from confinement in the thickets of the matted hair of the God

Paśupati” (V.31:bhuvana-trayaṁ Paśupater-jjat-antar-guhā-nīrodha-Parimōksha-Śighram-iva-Gaṅgaṁ p [ayah]) (Fleet ,1888, p.9).

The Bhera-ghat stone inscription of the queen Alhandevi frequently elucidates that *Gaṅgā* is very prominently illustrated as adorning the personality *Śiva*. According to the description of this inscription-“May those founts of holiness, the lines of the creeping and leaping tortuous waves of the river of heaven, meandering on *Śiva*’s head, guard you (those waves) about which the celestials are doubting whether they be lotus –garlands or lunar digits or sprouts of righteous deeds, or serpent skin or (the god’s) majesty bursting into views!”

kiṁ mālā kumudasya kiṁ śasikalāḥ

kindharmakarmākuraḥ

kiṁ vā kaṁcuki kaṁcukāḥ kimathavā

bhūtyudgamā bhāntyamī

itthannāki vitarkitāḥ śiva śiraḥ

saṁcāri nākāpagā

riṅgadvalgu taramga bhaṁgita tacāḥ

puṇya pravā pāntu vaḥ (V.2) (Kielhorn(1894) Pp. 10, 14)

The poet’s assumption put in an assortment of *Utprekṣā* here, is remarkable in the sense that the variety of Ganga he has deliberation or perceive (or for that substance, his divine has visualised) was not an embodied one but in a steam of water formed. Some of the assortment like that of lotus garlands or moon digits may be nearer to the actual depiction of stream, as observed in the field of visual arts.

1. *Om Om namaḥ Śivayā||*

2. Krauñch-ari-dvirad-āsyayōḥ śīsutayā tātasya maulau mithō gaṅgā

3.-vāriṇi khélatōḥśāsi-kalām= ālōkya madhyéjaṭam| sévāl-āvali-madhya-va(ba)ddha-śapharī

4.-vu (bu) ddhyā samākarshatōr-ākrandā-sphuṭa-kandaleéna vihasann=avyaj=jagad=

Dhūrjjaṭih/(Banerji ,1919-20, p.282; Majumdar, 2003, p.61)

The assertion of the inscription as *Gaṅgā-vāriṇi khélatōḥ*etc., indicates the form of Śīva as *Gaṅgadhara* where *Gaṅga* is again supposed to be shown in her stream form. The thought is further appropriately described in various later dated *Stotras* on Śīva. For illustration the line of the legendary Śīva – *tandavastoram* start as *jatātavī galajjalapravāha pātitasthāle* etc.

The Anuliya (Majumdar,2003, p.85) and Govindapur (Majumdar, 2003, p.94)copper plate inscription of Laksmanasena (12th century A.D),vividly described the water of the Ganges in several lines.

vidyudyatra maṇidyutiḥ phaṇipater

bbālendur indrāyudham/

vāri-svarga-taraṅgini sīta

śīromālā balākāvalih/

dhyānābhyāsa samīraṇīya nihito

śreyoṅkurodbhūtaye/

bhūyādvah sa bhavārti tāpa bhiduraḥ

śambho kapardāmbudahaḥ/

“May that cloud, namely the matted hair of *Sambhu*, which removes the heat of suffering of (this) existence having the flash of the jewel of the lord of the serpents as its lighting the crescent moon (on the fore-head

of the god) as its bow of Indra, the heavenly river as its water the string of white skulls as its line of cranes- and which contains within itself the air controlled by the meditation lead to the growth of the sprout of your (tree of) welfare”.

Another inscription, which is recovered from Harsha , a place called Rajathan during the reign of the Chahmana king Vigharaja (A.D.970) illustrated the force of the water of the river Ganges and her valour in noteworthy words (Kielhorn, 1894, pp. 119- 120).

vegoddhūrtāyamādi-graha gagana talaṃ
vyaśnuvānā jalaudhaiḥ/
nyak kurṣāṇā samudrān kṣaya valita jalān
ūrmi mālā sahasraiḥ//
deyādabhyarthitaṃ vaḥ śāśadharadhavalā
svardhunī candramaule/
maulau līlāṃ vahanī sphuṭa vikaṭa jaṭū
bandhane cīrikāyāḥ//

These lines highlight some important aspects of the Gaṅgadhara image. According to the inscription “May the river of heaven, who will her masses of water pervades the sky where the sun and the plants are shaken by her velocity and who with thousands of lines of her waves puts to shame the oceans with their decreasing water; who white like the moon, appears like a graceful veil on the crest of the moon-crested (god), fast bound with huge uncouth tresses of hair; may she grant your position”.

GANGADHARA IMAGE IN BENGAL

A magnificent image of *Gaṅgadhara* has been found from Deulbari area of South Twenty-Four Parganas, where a ruined temple is situated. The image highlights Lord *Pasupati* and her consort *Ganga* standing on an oval-shaped pedestal. The image of *Devi Ganga* shows her descent on earth from confinement in the matted hairs of the lord *Siva*. This sculpture has appeared as a stream of water as well as it is personified the *Devi Ganga*. The lord *Siva* embraces *Devi Ganga*. His left hand holds the left hand of the *Devi*, and his other hand holds the head of the *Ganga*. *Devi Ganga*

is situated separately from both legs of *Siva*. The slightly bent legs of the *Siva*, have been planted on a pedestal. The left leg of the *Devi Ganga* is placed on pedestal and the right one rests on the thigh of *Siva*. The bending of the right leg is meticulously carved. The well-laid-out drapery of the *Ganga* must be mentioned. The third eye of *Siva* is very prominently depicted. The *Devi* wears *kanthahara*, *Karnakundala* and *mekhala*. Whereas, *Siva* wears broad *kanthahara* and *kundala*. The oval-shaped face, sharp nose, well-curved eyebrows, emaciated lips and immaculate form of figures are important features of the images. The adipose body, broad chest and narrow lion waist are additional physiognomic characters of *Siva*. Beside this, the other physiognomic characters of the *Devi Ganga* are a lean body, well-shaped breast and slender waist. The auspicious smile is visible on the faces of both images. This terracotta plaque can be dated 7th /8th Century A.D.

CONCLUSION

The above-mentioned references highlight the textual as well as syncretic religious faith of the people. Some scholars opine that (Jash, 1974, pp. 176-177) this synthesis highlights the amalgamation of Aryan and non-Aryan culture in Hindu civilisation. The Brahmanical religion worshipped the river as a mother goddess. The divine forms of the goddess have appeared in the Vedas. Several hymns are dedicated to the rivers Saraswati and Ganga. It is a very important fact that the Aryan culture extended into the land of the seven rivers. This Aryan culture recognised the rivers as their goddess, and in India, the supreme position is the river Ganga. The earliest reference to the Pasupati form of *Siva* is recovered from a Harappan seal. Besides, this culture has been identified with the Dravidian or rather non-Aryan. This superficial assertion of the fusion of two separate icons belonging to two different groups may be endeavoured to synthesise the Aryan and the non-Aryan culture. This is the result of the river Ganga and *Siva* coming into close contact, and the non- Aryan culture expanded towards the middle and eastern India.

The significance of the image is this noteworthy specimen of art recovered in the lower part of the Gangetic delta. This area became important in different phases of the ancient period. The

inscriptional references highlight the land settlement of Brahmanical groups. The establishment of a number of temples has been found in this region by the inscriptional evidence. This plaque may be installed in this ruined temple. A considerable number of Saivaite icons were recovered from this area. Saivism as one of the most popular religious faiths established in this region of the Ganga.

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